

DETERMINANTS OF HEALTHCARE SERVICES UTILIZATION AMONG THE ELDERLY IN MBO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study was to investigate the Determinant of Healthcare Services Utilization among the Elderly in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The survey research design was adopted by the researchers for the study. Three research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study toward realising the research objectives. Purposive Sampling and snowball techniques were used to select elderly adults aged 50 - 80 years and above in the Mbo Local Government Area. The questionnaire was used in data collection for this study. The data collected were analysed quantitatively through the use of Pearson's Moment Product Correlation Coefficient (r). The results of data analysis showed that there exists a strong relationship between income, religious belief and education level of the elderly persons in the Mbo Local Government Area and their utilization of healthcare services at $r = -0.79, -0.91$ and -0.87 respectively. Anderson Health Care Utilization Model was employed by the researcher in the study. It was concluded that factors like availability, income level, religious belief and education level strongly affect the rate and level of utilization of healthcare services by the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area. The study recommended that the government of Akwa Ibom State should as a matter of urgency provide Mbo people with healthcare facilities as one hospital cannot care for the prevailing health needs of the Mbo people, especially the elderly in the Mbo Local Government Area.

KEYWORDS: Healthcare Services, Elderly, Mbo and Utilization

INTRODUCTION

Health for the elderly may be conceptualized as the ability to live and function effectively in society and to exercise maximum self-reliance and autonomy; it is not necessarily the total absence of disease (Harper, 1988). According to Titus, *et al.*, (2015), sound health is a fundamental requirement for living a socially and economically productive life. Poor health inflicts great hardships on households, including debilitation, substantial

monetary expenditures, loss of labour and sometimes death (Ononkpono *et al.*, 2020). Elderly Africans, like elderly Black Americans, tend to perceive their health according to their ability to perform activities of daily living and not according to laboratory or x-ray findings (Harper, 1988). For this study, the elderly are adults who are between the ages of 60 years and above found in rural areas.

The health status of adults affects their ability to work and thus underpins the welfare of the household, including the children's development (Asenso-Okyere, *et al.*, 2011). Poor health affects productivity in old age and health-treatable problems become complicated and sometimes lead to an untimely death when there is no access to healthcare services, especially by the older people. Life is worth living and comfort is enhanced in good health backed up with good healthcare provision and accessibility (Ononkpono *et al.* 2020). Age is expected to be positively related to the utilization of health facilities (Dias *et al.*, 2008). The level of accessibility of healthcare services by the elderly in Nigeria depends on the state of the healthcare services in Nigeria.

The World Health Organization (WHO) in Innocent *et al.*, (2014), describes health as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Health care delivery in Nigeria operates in the three tier of government; local, state and federal. This accounts for the disparities in quality, availability, cost and level of utilizations in the health sector in Nigeria. According to Kajang (2004), the Nigerian health care delivery system has undergone tremendous policy changes over the years. In the immediate post-colonial Nigeria, the health sector like other sectors of the economy was heavily subsidized. With the introduction of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), which witnessed the massive withdrawal of state subsidies from the health sector in 1986, health care delivery became privatised (Kajang, 2004). The Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) policy continued into the 1990s and 2000s and it has given place for drug vendors in the health sector due to the economic situation of the nation (Wilson *et al.*, 2020). According to Kajang, (2004), we can therefore locate contemporary health care delivery system in Nigeria within a market whereby the government has left the sector to private and business operators to invest their money and make profit from the health sector in an uncontrollable market price. Although the major source of her health care financing is derived from a free market economic system through the private sector, external funding from the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and many other multi-lateral donor agencies, there are other sources such as government (public sector) and voluntary organizations (Kajang, 2004).

Access to healthcare services is a multidimensional process involving the quality of care, geographical accessibility, availability of the right type of care for those in need, financial accessibility, and acceptability service (Peters, Garg, Bloom, Walker, Brieger, and Rahman, 2008). The utilization of healthcare services is related to the availability, quality and cost of services, as well as social-economic structure, and personal characteristics of the users (Onah *et al.*, 2009). Accessing health care in rural areas is confounded by problems such as insufficient health infrastructure, the presence of chronic diseases and disabilities, socioeconomic and physical barriers (Ricketts, 2009). The elderly are mostly found in the rural areas in Nigeria. This obviously placed them within the local government level of health care provisions. According to Hamid *et al.*, (2005), many low-income countries, Nigeria inclusive, have not been able to meet the basic healthcare needs of their people, especially those in the rural areas.

The elderly in Akwa Ibom State are within the class of citizens that are classified into the aged, and old age is characterized with fading in body composition and different kinds of diseases which make their level of need of healthcare services to be on high demand. The elderly are in most cases facing neglect by the people and the government (Usoro and Peters, 2019). Health crises like stroke, rheumatism, pains, partial and complete blindness, diabetes, hypertension, and paralysis which contribute to both physical and psychological health challenges have been known issues elderly in Akwa Ibom State. The majority of the elderly in the Mbo Local Government Area are living in abject poverty, while few depend on their children and relatives, many; especially the aged women are engaged in petty trading for survival. Since the majority of the elders in the Mbo Local Government Area are poor, utilization of healthcare seems to be a serious challenge as most of them consider healthcare service as a project made for the rich. Illiteracy and poverty seem to be the characteristics of the majority of elderly in the Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. These characteristics (illiteracy and poverty) have various ways of putting this class of citizens in bad health situations (Peters. *Et al.*, 2020). If this class of citizens are not taken care of, the majority of them will continue to struggle with bad health conditions and eventually die. If healthcare services in the Mbo Local Government Area are not transformed to solve the aged health problems, the aged population will diminish or suffer extermination in a few years to come.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The major objective of the study is to examine the determinants of healthcare services utilization by the elderly in Akwa Ibom State.

The specific objectives are:

- i. To investigate if income is a determinant factor in healthcare services utilization among the elderly in Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. To find out whether religious belief is a determinant factor in healthcare services utilization among the elderly in Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. To investigate if educational level is a determinant factor in healthcare services utilization among the elderly in Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated in line with the research objectives to guide the study.

Hypothesis One:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between income level and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in the Mbo Local Government Area.

Hypothesis Two:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between religious beliefs and utilisation of health care services among elderly persons in the Mbo Local Government Area.

Hypothesis Three:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between education level and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in the Mbo Local Government Area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Income and Health Care Services

Economists have attempted to understand the determinants of healthcare use and expenditure for a long time, and a fundamental question has been about the nature of healthcare

as an economic good (Grossman 1972). The expectation that healthcare use would increase disproportionately as income increases (the 'luxury good hypothesis') has dominated the debate. Numerous studies have examined this question by quantifying the income elasticity of healthcare (Costa-Font, McGuire, and Stanley 2012). However, in most studies, the fundamental assumption that income is exogenous is likely to be violated. For instance, individuals in poor health may be less likely to participate actively in the labour market, but at the same time consume more healthcare, the income and healthcare association are unlikely to be causal (Costa-Font et al. 2012).

Healthcare services have been a serious issue for the lower class in Nigeria due to the capitalistic practices of the health sector in the nation. It has become a threat to the poor. In some local government areas in Akwa Ibom state, health care services are like gambling to the lower class (Peters and Bassey, 2020). Most of the low-income earners do not consider healthcare services as readily available for their class. While income and health are in the form of constraints that an individual faces, the individual has choices which are motivated by preference maximisation (researchgate, 2024).

Education and Healthcare Services utilization

The inability to read and understand basic medical instructions may be an important barrier to receiving proper health care (American Medical Association, 1995). The relationship between education and health is never a simple one. Poor health not only results from lower educational attainment, it can also cause educational setbacks and interfere with schooling (Baum, Ma, and Payea, 2013). Until recently, one of the most commonly held views in economics has been that healthcare is a luxury good. However, results supporting this view have come from studies examining health expenditure data, rather than healthcare use. This view has additionally been challenged by a study exploiting oil income shocks at an aggregate level (Acemoglu *et al.*, 2013). Further, most of the research to date does not distinguish between preventive and curative health services. Finally, in health systems where there is mainstream public health insurance, a windfall of income might simply lead individuals to switch to private healthcare. It is important to understand how individuals' decisions about public and private healthcare are determined by income because these decisions influence support for public sector provision (Propper 2000). Factors influencing the utilization vary from locality to locality and within the same area, variation does occur but generally, illiteracy, poverty, cultural and religious beliefs and poor access have been identified as factors militating against utilization (Adamu and Salihu, 2002).

Safe Motherhood Project, Nigeria Final Report (2007) results also reveal the important finding that among women with less than a secondary school education, health facility deliveries were significantly higher in Gwoza compared to the control group. Seventy-two per cent of women in Gwoza delivered their last child (within the life of the project) in a health facility versus 40 per cent in the control community. Among women who had completed secondary school or higher, results were 85 per cent in Gwoza and 75 per cent in the control community.

Religious belief and healthcare

The role that quality of health care plays in the decision to seek care is related to people's own assessment of service delivery which largely depends on their own experiences with the health system and those of people they know (Anum, 2015). The two mechanisms through which quality of care affects the decision to seek care are satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the outcome, for example, the effectiveness of the treatment and remedies prescribed and satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the service received (Anum, 2015). An important factor in the utilization of maternal health and nutrition services is the socio-cultural background of the user, which determines the beliefs, attitudes, and perceptions she has concerning the service being offered (Jirnaló, 2008). Beliefs, attitudes and perceptions have a way of affecting healthcare services utilization across the different categories of people anywhere in the world.

According to Jirnaló (2008), a formal service that is respectful of the role played by traditional systems of health care and one that is flexible enough to incorporate medically harmless beliefs and practices from that system is most likely to succeed in winning the acceptance of the community. The extent to which the formal health service is congruent, or not in sharp conflict with some of the more fundamental indigenous tenets of health care, is one important determinant of its acceptability. A healthcare service system that ignores the local healthcare system is likely to shut out its potential users from the very outset even when it meets objective medical standards of excellent service (Jirnaló, 2008).

Theoretical Framework

The Health Care Utilization Model

The Health Care Utilization Model was propounded by Anderson in 1983. According to Okumagba (2011), Anderson and Neuman (1975) grouped in a three-sequence cluster of factors, which are pre-disposing, enabling and need factors that are capable of influencing health behaviour. This model was developed to investigate the use of biomedical health services. Other versions have extended the model to include other health care sectors, that is, traditional medicine and domestic treatment. The model as illustrated in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1

The model as illustrated in Figure 1 shows the different categories that give rise to healthcare utilization. The various factors organized in the different categories of the Health Care Utilization Model are as follows:

Predisposing Factors: These include age, gender, religion, global health assessment, prior experience with illness, formal education, general attitude toward health services, knowledge of illness, etc.

Enabling Factors: These include availability of services, financial resources to purchase services, health insurance, social network support, etc.

Need Factor: Perception of severity, total number of sick days for a particular illness, total number of days in bed, days missed from work or school, help from outside from caring, etc.

Healthcare Service Use (Treatment Action): Includes home remedies (herbal,

pharmaceuticals), pharmacy over counter drugs, from shops, traditional healers, private and public and private health services etc.

METHODOLOGY

The study examined the determinants of healthcare service utilization among the elderly in the Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. The study adopted a survey research design because the study is intended to acquire information on the determinants of healthcare services utilization among the elderly in the Mbo Local Government Area. The researcher made the study in such a way that various quantitative primary data collection techniques were employed. This is to make it convenient to examine the health situations of the elderly in the Mbo Local Government Area.

Since the population “P” of elderly persons aged 50 – 80 years and above in the Mbo Local Government Area is known to be 5,715, to determine the sample “n” the researchers use the formula as provided by Kothari (1990) to get a sample size of 192. Data was collected through the use of a questionnaire. The questionnaires were structured with close-ended questions which make it easy for the respondents to provide unbiased answers in objective manners. Data collected by the researchers were analysed through the use of statistical analysis involving tables of frequency, percentage distributions, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and the use of Microsoft Office 2010 statistical analysis.

RESULT

Test of Hypothesis One

In Hypothesis One, the researchers sought to investigate whether:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between income level and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area.

The analysis of the responses to the questionnaire's section “Substantive Issues” statements by the respondents gives the following results;

Table 1: Observed Frequency for Hypothesis One

AGRRED	7	116	108	93	103	9	61	70	75	63
DISAGREED	117	11	13	5	9	59	4	1	19	17

(Source: Researchers' field work)

The researcher used the later (Excel 2010) and r = -0.79

COMPUTATION OF HYPOTHESIS ONE USING PEARSON'S PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION

(Source: Excel 2010)

The rule of interpretation of correlation coefficient states that; values near zero imply a weak relationship, whereas values closer to either +1 or -1 indicate a stronger relationship.

Analysis of Calculated Results for Hypothesis One

According to figure 3, the Pearson Moment Product correlation Coefficient analysis of the relationship between income level and healthcare utilisation among the elderly persons as obtained from the respondents, shows that there exist a strong relationship between income level and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. This is derived from Pearson Moment Product correlation Coefficient of Hypothesis Two which gives -0.79. This shows that income of the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area greatly relate with their level and rate of healthcare services utilisation in Akwa Ibom State. The implication is that many of the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area who are poor cannot afford most of the healthcare services available at hospitals and other health care providers in Mbo Local Government Area.

Test of Hypothesis Two

In Hypothesis Two, the researcher sought to investigate whether:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between religious beliefs and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area.

The analysis of the responses to the questionnaire's section “Substantive Issues” statements by the respondents gives the following results;

Table 2: Observed Frequency for Hypothesis Two

AGRRED	2	4	65	86	103	9	9	91	74	71
DISAGREED	120	108	15	13	7	61	71	21	19	11

(Source: Researchers' field work)

The researchers used the later (Excel 2010) and r = -0.91

COMPUTATION OF HYPOTHESIS TWO USING PEARSON'S PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION

Fig. 4: Pearson Moment Product correlation Coefficient of Hypothesis Two

(Source: Excel 2010)

The rule of interpretation of correlation coefficient states that; values near zero imply a weak relationship, whereas values closer to either +1 or -1 indicate a stronger relationship.

Analysis of Calculated Results for Hypothesis Two

According to figure 2, the Pearson Moment Product correlation Coefficient analysis of the relationship between religious belief and healthcare utilisation among the elderly persons as obtained from the respondents, shows that there exist a strong relationship between religious belief and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. This is derived from the Pearson Moment Product correlation Coefficient of Hypothesis Three which gives -0.91. This shows that religious belief of the elderly persons plays key role in the utilisation level of healthcare services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The implication of the gathered data is that many of the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area seek spiritual helps from God through prayer houses and spiritualists more than they patronize hospital or health care centres within Mbo Local Government Area.

Test of Hypothesis Three

In Hypothesis Three, the researcher sought to investigate whether:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between education level and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area.

The analysis of the responses to the questionnaire's section “Substantive Issues” statements by the respondents gives the following results;

Table 3: Observed Frequency for Hypothesis Three

AGRRED	43	107	74	97	8	67	73	87	81	13
DISAGREED	23	3	14	2	78	59	9	17	12	93

(Source: Researcher's field work)

The researcher used the later (Excel 2010) and $r = -0.87$

COMPUTATION OF HYPOTHESIS THREE USING PEARSON'S PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION

Fig. 4: Pearson Moment Product correlation Coefficient of Hypothesis Three

(Source: Excel 2010)

The rule of interpretation of correlation coefficient states that; values near zero imply a weak relationship, whereas values closer to either +1 or -1 indicate a stronger relationship.

Analysis of Calculated Results for Hypothesis Three

According to figure 4, the Pearson Moment Product correlation Coefficient analysis of the relationship between education level and healthcare utilisation among the elderly persons as obtained from the respondents, shows that there exist a strong relationship between education level and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. This is derived from the Pearson Moment Product correlation Coefficient of Hypothesis Two which gives -0.87. This shows that the education level of the elderly persons has significant effect on the level and rate of healthcare services utilisation among the elderly in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. This implies that many of the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area are illiterate and their education statuses greatly influence their attitudes toward utilisation of healthcare services in Mbo Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study sought to examine the determinants of healthcare services utilization among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Three research hypotheses were considered by the researchers for the study. After using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient analytical methodology for the analysis of the findings through questionnaires, the researchers observed that for hypothesis one; the analysis of the Pearson's Moment Product correlation Coefficient analysis result shows that; there is a strong relationship between income level and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. According to findings by

the researcher, there exist high level of poverty among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area and this status has exert great influence on health management and health care services utilization among the elderly persons. Due to low level of income of the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, many of them have decided to seek health treatment and healing from other sources like, prayer houses, spiritualists, herbs use and chemists.

For hypothesis two, the analysis of the Pearson's Moment Product correlation Coefficient analysis result shows that; there is a strong relationship between religious belief and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. According to findings, this implies that many of the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area are of Christian religious faith and this status to a greater extent exerts great influence on how and where they seek health care services. It was discovered by the researcher that many of the respondents believed in faith healing and therefore sought spiritual help more than Western medicine and healthcare provisions.

For hypothesis three, the analysis of the Pearson's Moment Product correlation Coefficient analysis result shows that; there is a strong relationship between education level and utilisation of health care services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. According to findings by the researcher, there exists a high level of illiteracy among the elderly persons in the Mbo Local Government Area and this status has exerted great influence on where and how they go about their health management, and their options when it comes to health care services utilization. Findings show that many of the elderly persons in the Mbo Local Government Area are ignorant of the benefits of seeking healthcare services from trained healthcare providers in the hospitals. It was also part of the findings that many of the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area are afraid of communicating in English language with the health care providers in the hospitals due to their high level of illiteracy.

Conclusively, the findings of the three hypotheses show that availability of health care services, income level, religious belief and education level are determinant factors of health care services utilisation among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The findings imply that there exists a low level of utilization of healthcare services among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

In this study, data were collected and analysed quantitatively through the use of Pearson's Product moment Correlation Coefficient (r). The study which sought to investigate the determinants of healthcare services utilization among the elderly in Akwa Ibom State a case study of Mbo Local Government Area. The analysis of all the responses and data collected by the researcher shows that the findings of the three hypotheses indicate that income level, religious belief and education level are determinant factors of health care services utilisation among the elderly persons in Mbo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. These findings imply that there exists a low level of utilization of healthcare services among elderly persons in the Mbo Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher derived the following recommendations;

1. The government should come out with special healthcare programmes for the elderly

- persons to ensure their survival and good health stability.
2. Healthcare services providers and workers at various healthcare centres and hospitals should give priority of service to the elderly.
 3. The government should build special health care centres for the elderly to increase and encourage their health-seeking behaviour.
 4. Government should checkmate the activities of prayer houses in Mbo Local Government Area and the state at large in order to free our fathers and mothers who are held bond in deceit toward healthcare provisions and exploited by these so called prophets and prophetesses.

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